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Monkey Pox : A New Threat

Monkey pox is an infectious disease that can occur in humans and some other animals. Symptoms include fever, swollen lymph nodes, and a rash that crusts over. The time from exposure to onset of symptoms ranges from five to twenty-one days. The duration of symptoms is typically two to four weeks. There may be mild symptoms, and it may occur without any symptoms being known. The classic presentation of fever and muscle pains, followed by swollen glands, with lesions all at the same stage, has not been found to be common to all outbreaks. Cases may be severe, especially in children, pregnant women or people with suppressed immune systems.

The disease is caused by the monkeypox virus, a zoonotic

virus in the genus Orthopoxvirus. The variola virus, the causative agent of smallpox, is also in this genus. Of the two types in humans, the West African type causes a less severe disease than the Central African (Congo basin) type. It may spread from infected animals by handling infected meat or via bites or scratches. Human-to-human transmission can occur through exposure to infected body fluids or contaminated objects, by small droplets, and possibly through the airborne route. People can spread the virus from the onset of symptoms until all the lesions have scabbed and fallen off; with some evidence of spread for more than a week after lesions have crusted. Diagnosis can be confirmed by testing a lesion for the virus's DNA.

TRANSMISSION

Humans can be infected by an animal via a bite or scratch, bush meat preparation, or by contact with an infected animal's bodily fluids or lesion material. The virus is thought to enter the body through broken skin, the respiratory tract, or the mucous membranes of the eyes, nose, or mouth.

Once a human is infected, transmission to other humans is common, with family members and hospital staff at

particularly high risk of infection. The virus can spread by respiratory (airborne) contact or by direct contact with an infected person's bodily fluids or during pregnancy from mother to fetus. There are indications that transmission can occur during sexual contact, with infectious monkeypox virus able to be isolated from semen samples. Prolonged shedding in seminal fluids has raised the possibility of a genital reservoir for monkeypox virus. The virus can also spread through

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indirect contact with lesion material, such as through contaminated bedding, even with standard personal protective equipment, likely through inhalation. Risk factors for transmission include sharing a bed or room, or using the same utensils as an infected person. Increased transmission risk is associated with factors involving the introduction of virus to the oral mucosa. It is not yet known if people without symptoms of monkeypox can spread the virus.

Further research about the transmission of the strain responsible for the 2022 outbreak is ongoing, but it is not thought to be different from other strains of the West African clade.

PREVENTION

Vaccination against smallpox is assumed to protect against human monkeypox infection because they are closely related viruses, and the vaccine protects animals from experimental lethal monkeypox challenges. This has not been conclusively demonstrated in humans because routine smallpox vaccination was discontinued following the eradication of smallpox.

Smallpox vaccine has been reported to reduce the risk of monkeypox . The decrease in immunity to poxviruses in exposed populations is a factor in the prevalence of monkeypox.

Persons who have had close or intimate contact with individuals or animals confirmed to have monkeypox should also be vaccinated.

An infected person should be isolated in preferably a negative air pressure room or at least a private exam room to keep others from possible contact

OUTCOME

After healing, the scabs may leave pale marks before becoming darker scars. The risk of death in those infected ranges from 0% to 11%, depending on the type of monkeypox and location in the world. Most reported deaths have occurred in young children and people with HIV.

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